

Raquel Varela Michael Roberts
interview:
Time is running out

Michael Roberts (1946) is a leading Marxist economist. Michael Roberts has worked in the City of London for more than thirty years as an economist and financial adviser. He is author of several books including *The Great Recession*, *The Long Depression* and *Marx 200*. He blogs at thenextrecession.wordpress.com. With his charming British humour, and his highly pedagogical style, we interviewed him in the New Forest, a beautiful area in the southwest of the UK where he now lives.

HOW HAVE YOU BECOME A MARXIST ECONOMIST, A CRITICAL ECONOMIST?

Well, I come from a middle-class background. The family were doctors, generally, a lot of doctors! My father was a research chemist. But he died young, when I was only five. So my mother brought up myself and my sister. My mother was an art teacher and artist.

We became a bit separated from the rest of the family, who were conservative middle-class people in the north part of Britain and we didn't live there. And my father was always a bit of a rebel or "black sheep" from the rest of the family. And my mother was an orphan and rather bohemian. So after my father's death, we travelled around the world. So although I came from a very middle class background, my sister and I didn't have quite the same childhood development that most British middle-class people would have. That probably made me open to different ideas.

At school, I was probably a little bit of a rebel, even though I was obviously doing reasonably well in class and so on. I was always interested in politics. In fact, the "doctor family" was also interested in politics, only on the other side of the barricades! When I was at school, I thought I would be a Conservative and so read conservative newspapers at sixteen. At seventeen, I decided I was more of a liberal and so I would read the liberal newspapers. At eighteen, I decided I was a socialist and supported, as I come from Britain, the social-democratic Labour Party, when it was just coming into office after a decade or more of Conservative governments. I moved gradually further to the left. At school, when I was studying for my university entrance exams, the master said, well, what subjects do you want to do? Because you could do science, or you could do arts, you're not bad at both of them. So why don't you choose this new-fangled subject called economics? It's sort of in between. So I said, okay and I did economics and economic history for my university exams.

Now my father had gone to Oxford University, so I was applying for the Oxford and Cambridge and some other universities, like the London School of Economics. The master said at the time, said, well, that's good. But I just want to tell the class here that under no circumstances should anybody apply for this radically dangerous new university called the University of Sussex. This place is full of people who do not recognize traditional values and you shouldn't be going there. So I immediately applied for this college rather than go to LSE, which I could have gone to, or even possibly Cambridge. So I ended up going to the University of Sussex.

HOW WAS UNIVERSITY AT THE TIME?

For those of you who are very young, you won't realize that the mid-1960s was a period of quite radical, sharp change, particularly in mass pop culture, of young people having sufficient money and backing from a British welfare state to enable them to do so. When we went to university in the mid-60s, we didn't go to university looking for a job. That's the last thing we thought of because we had free tuition. We had grants (not

loans). And we had all kinds of other support from the state to enable us to go to university.

So we went to university basically to learn things and have a bloody good time! There was the idea of a wider, if you like, university for the right purpose, which was to develop your ideas in a free expression. And lots of the lecturers and even the officialdom of universities supported that idea. The idea that you had to join a business or a management school and get a job in finance, which is what everybody has to do now in this particular field, was completely ignored. If anything, if people wanted to get a job, they wanted to join the public sector. They wanted to work in government or in councils, to do socially good things. They didn't want to work in the private sector. It never entered their heads.

So it's a completely different transformation that we've seen over the last fifty years in the way that university students see what careers they should have and what direction they should take. This narrowing of their liberal arts understanding has come about in the drive by capital to ensure that it gets students to do things that are profitable.

At university, I'd moved already fairly far to the left. And then I came to read various Marxist works. And of course, at university, you find lots of people who are similarly thinking along those lines, particularly in the mid-60s. So there were lots of Marxist or socialist groups being formed in the university, which you came into contact with.

BUT YOU CAME INTO CONTACT WITH TROTSKYIST GROUPS IMMEDIATELY?

Yes, mainly Trotskyist groups. It's a matter of chance sometimes, it depends which university you go to. At that time, if you went to a different university, you would have got a different set of Trotskyist groups or maybe the Communist Party or no Trotskyist groups at all, just maybe ordinary social democratic clubs and so on.

There were many Trotskyist groups then, the "57 varieties". I came into contact with different ones, but at the University of Sussex at that time, the two main groups were International Socialists, now called the Socialist Workers' Party in Britain, and Militant, which was the name of the newspaper for another Trotskyist group.

THE MILITANT GROUP WORKED INSIDE THE LABOUR PARTY?

Well, that was not the only difference between the two particular Trotskyist groups we're talking about.

Militant had differences with what was now the Socialist Workers' Party, In particular, it didn't consider that the Soviet Union, which of course still existed at that time, was a "state capitalist" or capitalist economy. Militant saw it as what it would call a workers' state that had become degenerated by bureaucracy. That meant you should support the Soviet Union against US imperialism, while criticizing the Soviet bureaucracy. The posi-

tion of the IS at the time on that issue was “neither Moscow nor Washington”. As far as they were concerned, they were equally bad imperialist powers, which was a view that was not adopted by the Militant tendency. I tended towards Militant from an economic point of view. There was a fundamentally different way of organizing the economy in the Soviet Union in the mid-60s than there was under American capitalism, in my view.

I think the other thing also was perhaps tactics. I think the Militant felt that there was a long period of boom ahead and therefore, you couldn't expect dramatic change in working class struggles (although, of course, in the 1970s that changed). The IS at the time was basically saying that there were workers' protests everywhere, and it's going to explode. I found that a bit unrealistic. That lack of realism was also found in the Socialist Labour League, which didn't appear at my university. It was quite large at the time. It was another faction of Trotskyism, which had split from the Fourth International. They called for a general strike nearly every day. I thought all these were unrealistic approaches. And I thought that the people who were running the tendency called the Militant in that university were the most serious people. So I tended to align with them and participated in their activities.

And as you pointed out, one of the tactics of Militant was to work inside the British Labour Party on the grounds that this was a trade union party. There were Labour Party activists, particularly younger ones, who were sympathetic towards Marxist ideas. So it would be wrong to reject anything to do with them because they were in the Labour Party, but also because the Labour Party had the mass support of the working class.

Therefore it was inevitable that there was going to be a battle for the ideas on what working class organisations should do. That would also take place in the Labour Party [rather] than just in the trade unions.

HOW LONG DID YOU STAY IN THE MILITANT?

Well, I suppose I became a member in the mid-60s. But I left in 1990, I think. So for those of you who can count, that is about 25 years.

DURING THAT TIME, WHAT WAS YOUR ROLE AS A MILITANT?

Well, being an activist. After a certain period, I actually became a full-time worker for the Militant. They paid me, listeners might like to know, a massive salary, living life basically of a billionaire mogul (ho, ho).

AND YOU WERE DIRECTED TO GO AND TRY AND RECRUIT PEOPLE TO THE TENDENCY IN THE UNIONS AND IN THE LABOUR PARTY?

I initially moved to the Midlands of England, the main centre of

which, for those who don't know the UK, was a city called Birmingham, where we had no support whatsoever, no contacts or anything. So I moved there and began to try and build a group in Birmingham. I had reasonable success. I managed to recruit some important shop stewards at the major auto factory. And I helped built a youth section in the Labour Party which was basically supporting the position of the Militant.

CHINA: THE TWIN MEETINGS - THE BIG FLOP

So in this period I wasn't doing economics, I wasn't doing any job at all, from the period leading the university right through the volatile period of the 1970s.

There were a lot of working class struggles in the UK in the 1970s, because that was a period when capitalist economies began to collapse as profitability fell in Britain and elsewhere. So capitalists began to reverse previous labour gains and instead try to crush labour movements.

In particular in the case of the UK, they wanted to defeat the miners who were seen as the most militant in the trade union movement. So there was a series of miners' strikes before the famous one of 1984. There were two big miners' strikes in 1972 and in 1974. And in 1974, by the way, they closed the mines down so much that electricity was reduced to three days a week. That's how powerful the miners were. Both of those strikes were won by the miners.

In 1974 the miners' strike led to a general election and the defeat of the Conservative government. At this point you could see a labour movement riding high. In the auto workers too, there were a number of strikes, with shop stewards in control of trying to maintain the position of wages and conditions in the big industries in the 1970s.

In the 70s it was then that we had these series of major confrontations, and it was only in the 80s that the miners were defeated under Thatcher. She came to power in 1979 and one of her key aims was to defeat the miners, which they'd failed to do in the 1970s.

In the early 1970s, Thatcher was the minister of education. Then kids used to have free milk and orange juice so that kids got to keep up their calcium etcetera. Kids had free hot meals at lunchtime. Thatcher ended all that.

Then from 1974 to 1979, the Labour Party was in control. They did not restore anything Thatcher had removed but they did not make any further cuts until the cost of living crisis in 1979, which led to the defeat of Labour in the election.

For those who know about the history of the 20th century labour movement in the UK, the miners' leader that we know of in the 1980s was called Arthur Scargill. He became the leader of the miners' union, as a radical socialist leader. But in the early 1970s, he was just the leader of one sector, the region of Yorkshire miners.

In Birmingham, there were mining areas all around and Bir-

mingham had a big coal depot where all the coal would come and then [be] distributed around the country. When the miners had a strike in 1972, nothing was done to stop the flow of this coal coming in and out. The depot had huge stocks and therefore could have maintained coal supply to industry and so on for the government for months.

I happened to notice that trucks were still going in and out of what was called the Saltley depot. So I went to the local trades union federation and I said, you know, they're breaking the strike, all this coal's going through. And they said, just go away, little boy (because you've got to remember I wasn't very old and they were venerable trade union leaders). They said, "No, no, there's no problem, you're talking nonsense." So I thought, well, I don't really think that's right. So I made a phone call to the Yorkshire miners. And lo and behold, I got Arthur Scargill on the phone.

And I said to Scargill, look, there's this coal depot and all this coal's going in and out. Within two days, they had thousands of miners there. And it was a major confrontation in that strike. During the picket, one lorry tried to barge its way through and hit an inspector of police and broke his leg.

YOU PLAYED A VERY IMPORTANT ROLE IN THAT STRIKE?

Well, I'd like to think so, there are pictures of me standing on the picket line looking like a little bit of an idiot alongside all these miners.

YOU EDITED THE MILITANT NEWSPAPER FOR A WHILE?

Yes, I became the editor of the paper for a while, which was extremely strenuous. It used up all your energy because it's 24 hours a day, seven days a week. You couldn't do anything else.

I was eventually burnt out a bit. So I stopped working full time and got myself a job and then a series of jobs through the 1980s onwards.

WHAT KIND OF JOBS?

Well, I started off becoming a trainee income tax inspector. I left that. Then I started doing, basically economics jobs.

I was working in various bank organisations as an economist of sorts in various occupations right through the 1980s into the 1990s. So really, often on my blurb, it says Michael Roberts worked for thirty years in banking in the city of London. But it that started really in 1980s, onwards.

YOU WERE AN UNDERCOVER TROTSKYIST IN THE CITY OF LONDON?

Well, it's a good question. In the daytime, I was being an econ-

omist for various finance capital institutions and telling clients whether they should buy or sell the dollar or invest in this or not. And in the evening, I'd be doing work for the left organisations or writing articles and doing that sort of thing.

I didn't start the blog, which maybe many readers may know about, until 2005, or writing in that sort of material and producing things while I was still working in banks at the same time and in investment.

WHY DID YOU START THE BLOG IN 2005?

Well, I decided that it was time to do something a bit more useful in terms of developing my understanding of the world economy and Marxist economics. And I felt that, for me, the best contribution I could make to developing the ideas of socialism and furthering the movement was to deal with economics; not just explaining Marxist economics, but also criticising mainstream economics to try to explain to people when they read in the newspapers, what it all meant. What are the theories adopted by the conventional economists who work for banks that I was working for and for universities, but also to explain what Marxist economics is.

In my view, the litmus test of the difference between conventional economics and Marxist economics was that Marx had a labour theory of value, i.e. why things are valued as they are, prices, that differs from all other theories. His theory of value is based on the idea that we have a mode of production in modern society where production isn't for what people need. Yes, it has to be useful, otherwise people wouldn't buy it. But the owners of capital and the means of production employ people not to make things that people need; they produce things to make money. General Motors did not build cars because it wanted to give everybody a car, it built cars to make profit, to make money out of it. So there's a basic contradiction between social needs and values and the private profit of capitalists. That is the essence of Marx's theory of value. It differs from any other theory of value.

YOU HAVE DEVELOPED IN A VERY PEDAGOGICAL WAY AND, IN MY VIEW, A VERY SERIOUS WAY IN THE RIGOUR OF DEBATE. YOU ARE NOT AFRAID OF DEBATE WHICH YOU KEEP IN DEBATING IDEAS, NOT PEOPLE. DO YOU THINK THAT YOUR MILITANCY AND BEING OUT OF THE ACADEMIC CIRCLE HELPED YOU TO DO THIS?

Well, there are two things that came from being a revolutionary activist, if you like. That is, you learn how to do things, you learn how to speak, you learn how to organise. Because anybody who's had an experience of this knows you've got to do your own thing, you've got to do your own articles, print your own paper, you've got to sell that paper, you've got to be able to speak at meetings, maybe you have to intervene at meetings when you're not on the platform and you're just trying to make a point from the floor. And you learn, or at least I tried to learn, not to get up and speak for 15 minutes and drive everybody mad but try to make one or two points, and how to present a speech and how to write. All these are skills

that you can learn from being a revolutionary activist.

On the other side, by not being an academic, I also learnt to remember what I am trying to do here. I'm trying to get people who want to be active to change society.

Yes, we need to understand theory as rigorously as we can and the evidence and so on. So we need an academic approach to many issues, but we don't need an academic approach that completely obscures and confuses people and is written in language that makes no sense, if it's too convoluted for any activist to get any idea of what it means. So I felt that my task was to try and give us a view about where we're going, economically primarily, but of course from economics everything else flows, in my view, and also to do that from the point of view of the activist.

The things I write, particularly on the blog, are often quite theoretical or very empirical with lots of charts and so on, because I want to make sure that it's strong enough to combat the position of conventional economics, and it's not just saying, oh, they're all capitalists. That's not very helpful to an activist. We want to know why we have slumps, why we have inflation, why is there inequality in the world, why are we not solving the question of climate change. These are theoretical, scientific things that we can analyse, and those questions we must explain as best, as plainly, and as clearly as possible, and not in academic language.

There's too much academic language which is too obscure. As we're talking now, I've been looking on the computer at some academic conferences coming up, and when I look at some of the papers being presented, I can't understand them. What use are they to anybody that's trying to change society if they're not clear about what they mean? And they're not. And that intellectual academic thing exists in the academic world. Academics want to make their niche, I can understand that. So they're going to say something which they think is special, and if they can coat it up in a language we can't understand, then it sounds special. That's a bit unfair, but of course not all academics are like that. But in sum, I think it has been an advantage not to have been a university lecturer.

WHAT DO YOU FORECAST FOR THE WORLD? HOW DO YOU SEE THE WORLD NOWADAYS? HOW DO YOU SEE IT AS AN ECONOMIST, AS A MILITANT, AS A SOCIALIST? HOW DO YOU LOOK TO THE WORLD AT THIS MOMENT? WITH HOPE? WITHOUT HOPE?

Do I have hope or am I pessimistic? Well, I'm realistic. In short, world capitalism is in the worst state that it has ever been. It is not delivering on raising the living standards of the majority of the world's eight billion people. Inequality between the rich and the poor globally is widening; global warming is causing substantial damage to the climate, the general environment and the planet's species.

Even on capitalism's own priorities, namely the profitability of capital, things are worsening – the profitability of capital on average globally is very low. So the likelihood of regular and recurring slumps in production and employment has risen. In the 21st century, we have just experienced the worst crises

in the history of capitalism (2008, 2020) since it became the dominant (even the sole) mode of production and social formation globally. Moreover, the struggle over which country or elite controls that production, investment, trade and finance is taking a more dangerous turn, with wars and growing conflict between the imperialist powers led by the US and resistant powers like Russia and China – in Ukraine, Israel and Asia.

I argued in a book back in 2016 that the world economy had entered a long depression where economic growth, living standards, investment and profitability of capital would stagnate. Previous such depressions have either ended after a series of severe slumps which eventually enabled profitability to be restored (late 19th century depression) or because a world war broke out (1930s). I am not sure which option will be taken this time as capital attempts to break out from the current depression. Either way, it won't be good for 'the many'. Do I have hope? The only viable agency for change is the working class of the world, i.e. all those who work for a living and cannot live off rents, profits or interest from the ownership of things. The working class constitute more than 90% of the world's adults and families. It is in their interest to cooperate to end capitalism. So objectively, they are the agency for change. And the working class has never been larger: "we are many, they are few". In that sense, I have hope.

But that objective power has not been turned into sufficient conscious collective action to change the world. Yes, class struggle is daily in strikes, protests, boycotts, etc. But mass actions (revolutions) are few and far between. And as we enter the third decade of this century, revolution seems a distant prospect – in that sense I am pessimistic.

But things can change. The major capitalist economies may get a new lease on life from new technologies that could inject a period of boom that actually strengthens labour, particularly in new industries, leading to new working class forces as agents of change over the next decade.

Alternatively, the forces of reaction could strengthen, as they did in the 1930s, weakening working-class struggle and opening the door to military or fascist regimes that could send us back to the dark ages.

These are the hopes and fears. As realists, we must navigate our way through these alternatives towards a better world for humanity and nature, based on collective cooperation and control of world's resources and human endeavour. Time is running out ■